

REBUILD

Working Paper

**The evolution of conditionality in EU
financial assistance under the
Recovery and Resilience Facility**

Niall Moran

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

REBUILD Centre – Working Paper 5
February–2023

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Education and Culture Executive Agency (EACEA). Neither the European Union nor EACEA can be held responsible for them.

The evolution of conditionality in EU financial assistance under the Recovery and Resilience Facility

Niall Moran *

Abstract: This article examines a new type of conditionality provided for in the EU's Recovery and Resilience Fund (RRF). Funding under the RRF is released where 'milestones' have been met and this article examines how these milestones have been formulated and applied in relation to the justice systems of three Member States—two at the heart of the rule of law crisis (Hungary and Poland) and one that has been more vigilant in terms of observing the rule of law (Italy). These differing cases are examined in order to give a comprehensive overview of conditionality under the RRF.

This article argues that if milestones become a regular and predictable feature of EU economic governance, then there must be serious consideration of the incentives they create. Where reaching a milestone results in the release of hundreds of millions of euros in financing, this may create a system that incentivises member states to drag their heels on certain reforms, knowing that at some point they can be used in a quid pro quo with Brussels in the areas where milestones have been set.

This article further examines how conditionality may be most effective in these varying circumstances and attempts to draw on lessons from EU and non-EU programmes that have employed conditionality. These include the programmes of the IMF, EU bailout programmes, the EU accession process, inter alia.

Keywords: Conditionality, Milestones, bargaining tools, rule of law crisis, European Union economic governance, Recovery and Resilience Fund.

* Assistant Professor in Economic Law, School of Law and Government, Dublin City University.

1. Introduction
2. The Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF)
3. Milestones under the RRF
4. Conditionality in the RRF, bargaining, and fundamental values
5. Conditionality in other programmes and treaties
6. The conditionality requirements under the RRF– learning from past experience
7. Conclusion

1. Introduction

The European Union (EU) response to the challenges brought about by the Covid-19 pandemic has included an economic recovery package of €750bn. This package mainly consists of the Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF), established under Regulation 2021/241, which is a recovery instrument that gives Member States access to grants and loans. Under the RRF, financial assistance will be subject to conditionality as a way of driving domestic reforms in recipient countries that align with EU priorities. The requirements for this new form of EU financial assistance include that Member States submit a ‘recovery and resilience plan’ setting out the reforms and investments to be implemented over a given period that will address challenges identified in the European Semester and country-specific fiscal recommendations that have been adopted by the Council.

This article examines this new type of conditionality, which will operate in the context of an investment package. One of the implications of this context is that the conditionality attached to loans or grants would be anticipated to be less controversial than it has been in other contexts (e.g. that of a bailout). This is because the negotiating hand of the recipient Member State is stronger and this should be reflected in the reforms agreed to in their recovery and resilience plans. This has not proved to be the case however for the NRRPs of Poland and Hungary as the conditionality attached to this financing seeks to address the rule of law crisis in these countries.

Each member state submitted a National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP) which the Commission had to assess within two months. Payment requests under NRRPs are subject

to the satisfactory fulfilment of relevant milestones and targets.¹ The provision of financing in exchange for the reaching of certain targets can be viewed as a form of conditionality. Conditionality is a relatively new phenomenon in relation to financial assistance in the EU. This article examines the legal framework for its operation and how it is operating in practice. It considers the concept of milestones and how they have been formulated and applied in relation to the justice systems of Italy, Poland and Hungary with regard to differences in content and procedure. It is important to understand how this new form of conditionality will operate in relation to Member States at the heart of the rule of law crisis, but also how conditionality will operate in under the NRRP of a Member State that is more vigilant in terms of observing the rule of law in order to give a comprehensive overview of conditionality under the RRF and the types of reforms that are recommended in this context.

This is a key area of concern in relation to the rule of law crisis and this article examines the appropriateness of this form of conditionality in seeking to address the rule of law crisis as well as how such conditionality may be most effective.

It further considers the evolution of conditionality in EU financial assistance, firstly examining conditionality in relation to the Rule of Law Conditionality Regulation (Reg 2020/2092) as well as in relation to other EU and non-EU programmes, such as those of the IMF. The robustness of the conditionality in some of these earlier instruments has been called into question and this article examines whether the conditionality requirements under the RRF have responded to this.

2. The Recovery and Resilience Facility

The EU's post-Covid-19 Recovery Fund is called 'Next-Generation EU' and it has a budget of €750 billion. Approximately 90% of NGEU funds are allocated to the Recovery and Resilience Facility (the 'Facility', or RRF) and this will be spent directly by the Member States.² Regulation 2021/241 establishing the RRF was adopted by the European Parliament and the Council on 11 February 2021. Regulation 2021/241 lays down the objectives of the Facility, how it is financed, and the rules for the provision of financing under it.

¹ European Council Conclusions, 17-21 July 2021, EU CO 10/20, para A19.

² Federico Fabbrini, EU Fiscal Capacity Legal Integration After Covid-19 and the War in Ukraine, OUP (2022) 51. See Table 3.1. showing that funding allocated to the RRF is €672.5 billion or 89.66% of NGEU funds.

NGEU depends on the Own Resources Decision (ORD) (Council Decision 2020/2053), which establishes the revenues of the EU budget and authorises the funding of NGEU through the issuance of debt. National parliaments began ratifying the ORD in Spring 2021 and Germany's Constitutional Court, the *Bundesverfassungsgericht* (BVerfG), refused to grant an injunction against its adoption.³ By 31 May 2021, the EU had received formal notifications of the adoption of the ORD from all 27 Member States.⁴ The ORD entered into force on 1 June 2021 and the EU was then able to start making funding available under the Facility from this date.

Under the Facility, Member States had the option of applying for grants, loans or both. The Commission's recovery plan proposed that two thirds of NGEU funds would consist of grants, with the remaining third being made up of loans. The European Council amended the plan for European recovery, reducing the value of grants to €390 billion from €500 billion and increasing loans from €250 billion to €360 billion.⁵ Only seven Member States have sought loans under the RRF to date (Greece, Italy, Cyprus, Poland, Portugal, Romania, and Slovenia) though it appears Hungary may seek loans of up to €9.6 billion.⁶ Grants were naturally seen as more attractive as they do not have to be paid back by the recipient Member State itself. Rather, grants will be repaid through new EU taxes. Tables 1.1, 1.2 and 1.3 set out the total amounts Member States are set to receive under the RRF.

³ This refusal was prior to the full hearing of the case See *Bundesverfassungsgericht*, The Federal Constitutional Court, Order of 15 April 2021 - 2 BvR 547/21. Available at: https://www.bundesverfassungsgericht.de/SharedDocs/Entscheidungen/EN/2021/04/rs20210415_2bvr054721en.html.

⁴ Council of the EU Press release, 'Green light from all member states for EU recovery spending', 31 May 2021. Available at: <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2021/05/31/green-light-from-all-member-states-for-eu-recovery-spending/>

⁵ See European Council Conclusions, 17-21 July 2021, EU CO 10/20, paras A5 & A6.

⁶ Tamas Csonka, Intellinews, 'Hungarian request for RRF loan boosts forint', 26 January 2023, available at: <https://intellinews.com/hungarian-request-for-rrf-loan-boosts-forint-268052/?source=hungary>

Table 1.1 Total loans and grants Member States are set to receive under the RRF

Table 1.2 Total grants Member States are set to receive under the RRF

Table 1.3 Total loans and grants Member States are set to receive under the RRF

		Grants (billions of euros)	Loans (billions of euros)	Total (billions of euros)
1.	Italy	68.9	122.6	<u>191.5</u>
2.	Spain	69.5	0	<u>69.5</u>
3.	France	39.368	0	<u>39.368</u>
4.	Poland	23.9	11.51	<u>35.36</u>
5.	Greece	17.77	12.73	<u>30.5</u>
6.	Romania	14.94	14.24	<u>29.18</u>
7.	Germany	25.613	0	<u>25.613</u>
8.	Portugal	13.9	2.7	<u>16.6</u>
9.	Czechia	7	0	<u>7</u>
10.	Slovakia	6.3	0	<u>6.3</u>
11.	Croatia	6.295	0	<u>6.295</u>
12.	Bulgaria	6.267	0	<u>6.267</u>
13.	Belgium	5.9	0	<u>5.9</u>
14.	Hungary	5.8	0	<u>5.8</u>
15.	Netherlands	4.7	0	<u>4.7</u>
16.	Austria	3.46	0	<u>3.46</u>
17.	Sweden	3.3	0	<u>3.3</u>
18.	Slovenia	1.8	0.705	<u>2.505</u>
19.	Lithuania	2.22	0	<u>2.22</u>
20.	Finland	2.085	0	<u>2.085</u>
21.	Latvia	1.8	0	<u>1.8</u>
22.	Denmark	1.5	0	<u>1.5</u>
23.	Cyprus	1.006	0.2003	<u>1.2063</u>
24.	Ireland	0.989	0	<u>0.989</u>
25.	Estonia	0.969	0	<u>0.969</u>
26.	Malta	0.3164	0	<u>0.3164</u>
27.	Luxembourg	0.093	0	<u>0.093</u>

Receiving funding under the Facility

To receive funding under the Facility, Member States were required to submit NRRPs by 30 April 2021 in order to comply with the requirements of Article 18 of Regulation 2021/241. Plans shall set out “envisaged milestones, targets and an indicative timetable for the implementation of the reforms, and investment...” (Article 18) and loans shall be paid “subject to the fulfilment of milestones and targets” (Article 14). As such, where funding is granted, Member States must enact agreed upon reforms and meet milestones or targets in identified areas in order to continue availing of the funding. The ceiling for grants that could be applied for was set with reference to the impact of Covid-19 on each Member State’s economy (as per Annex IV of the Regulation). Article 14(5) capped the maximum loan support available at 6.8% of its 2019 GNI in current prices. The four largest recipients under NGEU include Italy, Spain, France and Poland. Italy is set to receive €191.5 billion in funding under its recovery and resilience plan. This represents almost one third of NGEU, while Spain, France and Poland are set to receive €69.5 billion, €39.4 billion and €35.4 billion respectively.

By October 2021, 26 EU Member States had submitted their NPPRs and the Netherlands followed suit in July 2022. Despite the fact that several Member States missed the official 30 April 2021 deadline for submitting their plans, the Commission proposed to approve the NRRPs of all Member States with the notable exceptions of Hungary and Poland. Certain Member States began receiving their first tranches of funds from the Facility in August 2021.⁷

The use and continued disbursement of NGEU funds is subject to strict monitoring and Regulation 2021/241 contains several provisions on reporting. Firstly, the Commission must submit NRRPs to the European Parliament and the Council without undue delay (Article 25) and present a review to the European Parliament and the Council on how national plans contribute to the objectives of the Regulation (Article 16). Under Article 27, each Member State must present reports on the achievement of their plan twice per year. The Commission sets common indicators for reporting on progress as well as monitoring and evaluation of the Facility (Article 29). Article 30 provides that the Commission shall establish a scoreboard displaying progress on implementation of NRRPs. Finally, Article 31 provides that the Commission shall provide an annual report to the European Parliament and the Council on the implementation of the Facility.

⁷ E.g. ‘NextGenerationEU: European Commission disburses €24.9 billion in pre-financing to Italy’, 13 August 2021. Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_21_4066.

3. Milestones under the RRF

This section considers conditionality and how it operates under the RRF in relation to Italy, Poland and Hungary. There have also been early indications that Hungary and Poland will have the most difficulty complying with conditionality as set out under their NRRPs. It is also important to consider how conditionality will operate under the NRRP of a Member State where there is no rule of law crisis in order to give a comprehensive overview of conditionality under the RRF and the types of reforms that are recommended in this context. Italy is also the largest recipient under the RRF, while Poland is the fourth largest recipient.⁸ Hungary is set to receive €5.8 billion in funding as part of its recovery and resilience plan and is the fourteenth largest recipient under the RRF.

In June 2021, the European Commission positively assessed Italy's NRRP and Italy received its first tranche of financing of €24.9 billion in August 2021. By late 2021, the Commission had proposed the approval of the NRRPs of all Member States except for Hungary and Poland.⁹ European Commission President Ursula von der Leyen outlined three conditions related to the rule of law crisis, explained in Section 4 below, for Poland to receive this funding linked to the rule of law crisis in that country. These included that Poland “dismantle the disciplinary chamber, to end or reform the disciplinary regime, and to start a process to reinstall the judges”.¹⁰

Despite these pronouncements, the Commission endorsed Poland's NRRP in June 2022. This was referred to by one rule of law watcher as a capitulation.¹¹ In November 2022, The Commission endorsed Hungary's plan, but the disbursement of financing is subject to meeting ‘super milestones’ related to the rule of law. The milestones set out for Italy, Poland and Hungary are now examined.

Under the RRF, ‘milestones’ refer to qualitative goals (e.g. enacted legislation) while ‘targets’ refer to quantitative goals (e.g. square metres of buildings that are now energy efficient). NRRPs set out a mixture of milestones and targets that must be met in order for the payment of loans and grants under the RRF to be disbursed. Where any of the milestones or targets are not met, these payments may be suspended as per Article 24(6) of the RRF Regulation. By early 2023, Italy had reached 96 of its milestones and targets

⁸ See NGEU Tracker, National RRFs in detail, last accessed 8 February 2023. Available at: <https://www.ngeutracker.org/recovery-resilience-plans>.

⁹ The Netherlands did not submit its NRRP until July 2022.

¹⁰ See Politico, ‘Von der Leyen lays out path to unlock Polish recovery funds — with conditions’, 28 October 2021. Available at: <https://www.politico.eu/article/european-commission-ursula-von-der-leyen-sees-path-compromise-to-unlock-polish-recovery-funds/>

¹¹ Franz C. Mayer, ‘Die Kapitulation’, 2 June 2022. Available at: <https://verfassungsblog.de/die-kapitulation/>

set out in its Council Implementing Decision on the approval of the assessment of its recovery and resilience plan.¹² Neither Hungary nor Poland on the other hand had fulfilled any of the milestones or targets set out in their respective Council Implementing Decisions on the approval of the assessment of their recovery and resilience plans. This is partially due to the fact that their NRRPs were approved later than that of Italy. In December 2022, the Council approved an Implementing Decision on the assessment of Hungary's RRP, following the Commission's positive assessment.¹³ This section summarises the milestones set for Italy, Poland and Hungary that are related to the justice system under their NRRPs, before analysing and comparing them.

Milestones for Italy

Italy's RRP contains five main areas, one of which focuses on 'justice'.¹⁴ Issues identified in this area include the duration of civil and criminal proceedings and effectiveness in fighting corruption.¹⁵ Broadly speaking, reforms aim to simplify existing criminal and civil procedures while monitoring systems will be used to achieve higher productivity. To reduce the backlog of civil cases, proposed solutions include strengthened ADR and temporary hiring.

Of the milestones and targets Italy has already achieved, several of them have directly related to the Italian justice system and these have fallen into three broad categories: 1) Investment in the recruitment procedures for civil, criminal and administrative courts; 2) Reform of criminal justice; and 3) Reform of civil justice.

In terms of the first of these areas, investment in court recruitment procedures resulted in Italy reaching two milestones. These were reached initially in April 2022 with the entry into force of special legislation governing NRRP recruitment and subsequently with the start of the recruitment procedures for administrative courts in November 2022.

Secondly, in the area of reform of criminal justice, implementing legislation came into force in this area in late 2021 via Decree-Law No. 152/2021 and other secondary legislation. This reform aims to streamline criminal proceedings, strengthen monitoring

¹² See European Commission, Recovery and Resilience Scoreboard, Milestones and Targets. Last accessed 3 January 2023, available at: https://ec.europa.eu/economy_finance/recovery-and-resilience-scoreboard/milestones_and_targets.html?lang=en

¹³ Implementing Decision (EU) 2022/2506 on measures for the protection of the Union budget against breaches of the principles of the rule of law in Hungary, 15 December 2022.

¹⁴ Federico Fabbrini, EU Fiscal Capacity Legal Integration After Covid-19 and the War in Ukraine, OUP (2022) 106-120. See this chapter (Ch. 5) for a case study on Italy's implementation of NGEU.

¹⁵ See COM(2021) 344 final, Annex to the Proposal for a Council Implementing Decision on the approval of the assessment of the recovery and resilience plan for Italy {SWD(2021) 165 final}, 22 June 2021, 1-5.

of the courts, and introduce incentives to reduce the length of proceedings in all criminal courts.

Thirdly, for reform of civil justice, enabling legislation came into force in this area in late 2021 via Decree-Law No. 152/2021 and other secondary legislation. This reform aims to ensure binding time frames for proceedings, introduce mediation and alternative dispute resolution (ADR), strengthen monitoring systems, and increase the productivity of civil courts.¹⁶

On 22 June 2021, the European Commission positively assessed Italy's NRRP and the European Council approved Italy's plan on the same day. Italy received its first tranche of financing of €24.9 billion in August 2021. In November 2022, Italy's second tranche of payment was approved as Italy was found to have reached the 45 milestones and targets linked to the second instalment. A third tranche is linked to a further 55 milestones and targets and this may be paid in early 2023.

Milestones for Poland

Milestones for Poland aim at raising the standard of judicial protection thereby improving the investment climate. They are divided into six 'components', with component F concerning 'Quality of Institutions'. Component F contains three key milestones that attempt to go some way in addressing the rule of law crisis in Poland and these are labelled F1G, F2G and F3G. Milestone F1G is the most far-reaching and requires reform that would strengthen the independence and impartiality of courts. This milestone has five subheadings that cover: a) the scope of jurisdiction of the Supreme Court Chamber, other than the existing Disciplinary Chamber; b) clarifying the scope of judicial liability, by ensuring that the right to submit requests for preliminary rulings is not restricted; c) reform determining that the content of judicial decisions is not classified as a disciplinary offence; d) that in proceedings, it can be verified that judges meet the requirements of being independent, impartial and 'being established by law', according to Article 19 TEU where a serious doubt arises on that point; and e) that procedural guarantees are strengthened. Milestones F2G and F3G require reforms to remedy the situation of judges affected by the decisions of the Disciplinary Chamber of the Supreme Court in disciplinary cases and judicial immunity cases.

The Commission endorsed Poland's NRRP in June 2022. Commission President Von der Leyen had outlined the major conditions for Poland to receive funding under its NRRP in

¹⁶ See Italia Domani, the National Recovery and Resilience Plan, Progress on the implementation of the plan, last accessed 3 January 2023, available at: <https://www.italiadomani.gov.it/content/sogei-ng/it/en/home.html>

October 2021 and these included the dismantling of its disciplinary chamber, ending or reforming Poland's disciplinary regime, and the starting of a process for reinstalling former judges.¹⁷ Both the disciplinary chamber and the disciplinary regime appear to violate EU law by failing to demonstrate any degree of operational and investigative independence.¹⁸ The Commission's change in stance was not brought about by concrete improvements in the rule of law in Poland but rather seems to have been a reaction to the invasion of Ukraine and the difficulties encountered by Poland in the aftermath of this. This 'capitulation' faced an unusual level of resistance with five Commissioners, including Vice-Presidents Timmermans, Jourová and Vestager, voting against or submitting written concerns against the resolution.¹⁹

On 13 December 2022, Poland reached an agreement with the Commission on legislation that if enacted would lead to the release of funds.²⁰ It is unclear at present how far the proposed legislation will go in remedying key concerns that have long been outlined in relation to the rule of law crisis in Poland.

It appears that the invasion of Ukraine had an impact on the reaching of an agreement here. This led to an increased urgency in Poland to receive funding from the post-pandemic economic recovery package. Poland is tackling a cost-of-living crisis, inflation and high numbers of refugees arriving from Ukraine. While there is no legal reason for the Commission to relax its expectations in the area of the rule of law due to the invasion of Ukraine,²¹ it appears that the approval comes as an acknowledgement of Poland's efforts amidst a crisis unprecedented in modern times. While some acknowledgement of these efforts may be a good thing, the Commission must avoid any perception that the rule of law is negotiable and that cross-issue linkages can be made in a kind of bargaining process.

Milestones for Hungary

Hungary's 'super milestones' are listed in the Annex to the proposal for a Council

¹⁷ The disciplinary chamber refers to a unit established within the national prosecutor's office in 2016 tasked with investigating judges and prosecutors, as well as a new disciplinary regime for judges.

¹⁸ Opinion of Advocate General Bobek, Joined Cases C-83/19, C-127/19 and C-195/19, 23 September 2020, para 269.

¹⁹ Lili Bayer, Politico, 'Amid Commission rebellion, von der Leyen defends Polish recovery cash plan', 2 June 2022. Available at: <https://www.politico.eu/article/amid-commission-rebellion-von-der-leyen-defends-polish-recovery-cash-plan/>

²⁰ Bloomberg, Poland Agrees With EU on Legal Changes to Free Funds, 13 December 2022. Available at: <https://www.bloomberg.com/news/articles/2022-12-13/poland-says-agreed-with-eu-on-legal-changes-to-free-funds?sref=vtgjJEDZ%2520via&leadSource=uverify%20wall>

²¹ Franz C. Mayer, Die Kapitulation, 2 June 2022. Available at: <https://verfassungsblog.de/die-kapitulation/>

Implementing Decision on the approval of the assessment of Hungary's RRP.²² The Annex contains 270 milestones in total, 27 of which are rule of law related 'super milestones'. The label 'super milestone' relates to the fact that these safeguards must be put in place before any payment is authorised by the Commission.²³ These milestones relate to the prevention of fraud and corruption (160, 166, 169, 171), transparency surrounding public spending and public procurement (174, 175, 195, 197, 198, 200, 201), strengthening judicial independence (213-216), reinforced legal provisions setting out implementation arrangements guaranteeing the sound use of Union support in a manner free of corruption (217-221), effective use of Commission data-mining and risk scoring tools (222, 223), enhanced audit and anti-corruption controls for Union support and the RRP (224-228).

On 30 November 2022, the Commission presented its assessment of Hungary's performance under the conditionality procedure. It endorsed Hungary's NRRP conditional on the full and effective implementation of the 27 'super milestones'. Without attaining these milestones related to the rule of law, the Commission stated that "no payment under the RRF is possible".²⁴ The Commission has set these conditions out and the disbursement of financing is directly subject to their fulfilment. The Commission's resolve will undoubtedly be tested in 2023 but if it were to disburse €5.8 billion to Hungary without fulfilling these conditions, it would certainly lose credibility. The fact that this conditionality procedure has shown itself to have teeth is a victory for the rule of law in the EU, thus far at least.

The milestones for Italy, Poland, and Hungary are very different in the areas of justice and law reform in terms of their content as well as the extent to which they are pre-requisites for the release of funding under the EU's post-pandemic economic recovery package. Some milestones are more weighty than others. Milestone F1G for Poland is very broad and covers five areas of reform for Polish courts. Other milestones relate to more minor matters that can be remedied with an uncontroversial legislative provision, the publication

²² The relevant milestones for the rule of law are numbers 160, 166, 169, 171, 174, 175, 195, 197, 198, 200, 201, 213, 214, 215, 216, 217, 218, 219, 220, 221, 222, 223, 224, 225, 226, 227 and 228. See Annex 1 for the content of these milestones.

²³ Recital 56, Proposal For a Council Implementing Decision on the approval of the assessment of the recovery and resilience plan for Hungary, COM(2022) 686 final, 30 November 2022.

See also John Morijn (@JMorijn, 1 Decemebr 2022) <https://twitter.com/JMorijn/status/1598334122170015746>, last accessed 8 February 2023.

²⁴ European Commission, Press Release, Commission finds that Hungary has not progressed enough in its reforms and must meet essential milestones for its Recovery and Resilience funds, 30 November 2022. Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_22_7273

of a plan, etc.²⁵

Hungary's milestones in the area of justice and law reform are the most wide-ranging and they operate as pre-conditions for the receipt of funding under the RRF. Poland's milestones focus on three main areas, while Italy's relate to different areas, namely civil and criminal proceedings as well as anti-corruption. Unlike Poland, where the milestones in this area focus on judicial independence, Hungary's 27 super milestones concern a broader range of activities encompassing public spending and public procurement as well as audit and anti-corruption controls.

4. Conditionality in the RRF, bargaining, and fundamental values

This section considers the operation of the Rule of Law Conditionality Regulation, how conditionality operates under the RRF, and the appropriateness of linking funding to fundamental values of EU law.

Background

Rule of law backsliding began in the EU as early as 2011.²⁶ As per Article 2 TEU, "The Union is founded on the values of...the rule of law". The type of conditionality seen in the RRF builds on other responses to rule of law backsliding including Regulation 2020/2092, the Rule of Law Conditionality Regulation. Regulation 2020/2092 provides a general regime of conditionality for the protection of the EU budget as a means of countering backsliding in relation to the rule of law. This Regulation was conceived as leverage to counteract the erosion of the founding principles of the Union. The principles set out in this Regulation are to be observed by all Member States, though the withholding of funding on this basis has been primarily discussed in relation to Hungary and Poland.

Regulation 2020/2092 establishes rules for the protection of the Union budget where Member States breach principles underpinning the rule of law (Article 1). Article 2 recalls that the rule of law as a value is enshrined in Article 2 TEU and it includes legality, legal certainty, the prohibition of arbitrariness, judicial protection before independent and impartial courts, and access to justice. Breaches of these principles may arise where the

²⁵ For example, one of Slovakia's milestones was reached with the publication of an investment plan for railway infrastructure projects.

²⁶ Pech & Scheppele, 'Illiberalism Within: Rule of Law Backsliding in the EU', *Cambridge Yearbook of European Legal Studies* (2017) 19, 3-47.

independence of the judiciary is endangered, arbitrary decisions by public authorities are not sanctioned, or legal remedies are limited (Article 3). In order to reach unanimity at the European Council, detail on respecting the rule of law as a condition of receiving EU funding was avoided.²⁷

On 18 September 2022, the Commission recommended suspending €7.5 billion of Cohesion Funds under the Conditionality Regulation in addition to the €5.8 billion at stake that is linked to the RRF. Negotiations between Hungary and the Commission under the RRF and Conditionality Regulation took place in parallel but with different negotiators acting on each side. The receipt of this €7.5 billion in Cohesion Funds is conditional on Hungary enacting 17 reform and anti-corruption measures.²⁸ Some of these reform measures overlap with Hungary's 27 'super milestones' under its NRRP.

On 30 November 2022, the Commission presented its assessment of Hungary's performance under the conditionality procedure and concluded that the conditions for the application of the Conditionality Regulation remained unmet and maintained its recommendation of suspending €7.5 billion in Cohesion Funds.²⁹ On 12 December, the EU Council suspended €6.3 billion (84% of the amount recommended by the Commission) in Cohesion Funds to Hungary with a qualified majority agreeing to impose these measures for the protection of the Union budget. These measures can be reversed and Hungary will receive this funding if the situation is fully remedied within two years to the satisfaction of the Commission and the Council.³⁰

Conditionality and incentives under the RRF

Conditionality is defined here as arising where one party grants a benefit to another party and this is linked to the latter party taking some step that has been agreed upon by the parties. In terms of the RRF, conditionality arises as funding is released (the benefit) once certain milestones have been fulfilled (the step taken that is linked to the benefit). As seen with the milestones set for Italy, for member states that have not allowed any rule of law backsliding to occur, further milestones are set in this area which must be achieved in order to access RRF funding. Does such a system incentivise member states to drag their heels on certain reforms, knowing that at some point they can be used in a quid pro

²⁷ European Council Conclusions, 17-21 July 2021, EU CO 10/20, para A24.

²⁸ See Annexes to the Explanatory Memorandum of the Commission proposal for a Council implementing decision on measures for the protection of the Union budget against breaches of the principles of the rule of law in Hungary, 18 September 2022. Available at: https://commission.europa.eu/system/files/2022-09/com_2022_485_1_en_annex.pdf

²⁹ Press Release, European Commission, 30 November 2022. Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_22_7273

³⁰ See Press Release, Council of the EU, 12 December 2022. Available at: <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2022/12/12/rule-of-law-conditionality-mechanism/>

quo with Brussels?

If this form of conditionality represents a new system of economic governance, the Commission needs to think carefully about the incentive structures that it will bring about. Reaching the milestones agreed with the Commission translates into valuable grants and loans for governments. In 2022, Italy reached 96 milestones and received €45.1 billion in grants and loans. In 2021-22, Spain reached 92 milestones and received €22 billion in grants and loans. Thus reaching a milestone set out in a member state's Council Implementing Decision on their NRRP is very valuable. On average, each milestone reached was worth €469 million for Italy and €239 million for Spain during this period. While the value for Italy is higher, it must be recalled that its funding relates to both loans and grants.³¹ Spain's funding reflects grants alone.

In December 2021, Spain reached one of its milestones with the entry into force of by-laws on equal pay between women and men. If measures to close the gender gap can be leveraged to unlock hundreds of millions in EU grants, this could potentially disincentivise such reforms at the domestic level. Member states may think twice before enacting reforms if these reforms will become valuable bargaining tools with Brussels. This would particularly be the case if the agreement of milestones with the EU were to become a regular and predictable feature of EU economic governance. When an entity (a state, an organisation etc.) is paid for carrying out certain acts, they become used to this. Likewise, if you pay your child €2 to go to the shop, they may expect this the next time you ask them to go to the shop. Worse still, if member states that have regressed in areas where the Commission has set milestones receive payment for bringing their standards back to where they originally were, this may incentivise the lowering of standards in all of the areas where the Commission has set milestones.

Vigilance in terms of the rule of law, or any area where the Commission sets milestones, must be rewarded. Finding a system that does this well is complicated but may, for example, involve setting milestones that are more investment-focused rather than reform-focused for vigilant member states.

Where a member state reaches a milestone, it is unclear what would happen if it were to regress in this area once funding from the RRF has been received. If a member state were to undo a reform for which it had received EU funding, there should be a mechanism in

³¹ The value of milestones for Italy here reflects both grants and loans because there is no clear division between the disbursement of funds into grants and loans. Funding by way of grants and loans is disbursed to those Member States receiving both when a series of milestones and targets are met. E.g. Italy received its second tranche of funds under the Facility for reaching 45 milestones and targets. The €21 billion euros disbursed was made up of €10 billion in grants and €11 billion in loans.

place to penalise that member state through an obligation to repay or the withholding of future payments under another instrument such as the multiannual financial framework (MFF).

Fundamental EU values

While justice reforms under the RRF such as reductions in the length of proceedings may be difficult to oppose, concerns have been raised where milestones relate to fundamental values of EU law, which have always been binding on EU member states. Alemanno argues that labelling compliance with EU law as milestones “produces the perverse effect of providing financial incentives to comply with pre-existing and generalised legal obligations that bind all Member States”.³² This raises the question of whether there can be any legitimacy to milestones relating to compliance with pre-existing obligations under EU law.

Rewarding member states financially for complying with fundamental EU values, such as the rule of law, creates perverse incentives.

Funding from the EU’s post-pandemic economic recovery package certainly represents a carrot for those member states that have regressed in relation to the rule of law. However, the rule of law crisis is arguably the most serious crisis the EU has faced among a strong list of contenders (the euro crisis, the refugee crisis, Brexit, etc). It has been described as the only one that poses a potentially existential threat to the Union as a political and legal order.³³

The EU must show resolve in withholding funding on the basis of this fundamental issue. Releasing funds based on an unrelated issue (such as Poland’s acceptance of refugees from Ukraine) would only highlight the perception that the rule of law is negotiable. There is a question as to whether the achievement of these milestones would represent a turning of the tide in this crisis. Any measure that would be deemed to fulfil Milestone FIG for example would have to be enduring and ensure that there would be no volte-face once EU recovery funds are received. The pragmatism these milestones represent could only be considered to be a positive step if they bring about their stated goals in an unequivocal and enduring manner.

Alemanno is of the view that with this system of milestones, the Commission is “de facto prolonging, and therefore worsening, the effects stemming from [Poland]’s rebellious

³² Alberto Alemanno, ‘Censuring von der Leyen’s Capitulation on the Rule of Law,’ *VerfassungsBlog*, 8 June 2022. Available at: <https://verfassungsblog.de/censuring-von-der-leyens-capitulation-on-the-rule-of-law/>

³³ R. Daniel Kelemen, *Encompass*, ‘Europe’s quiet crisis,’ April 2021. Available at: <https://encompass-europe.com/comment/europes-quiet-crisis>

non-compliance with the EU legal order”.³⁴ The Union does indeed find itself in a bad and tricky situation in relation to the rule of law crisis and there are strong arguments for wielding a stick, rather than dangling a carrot. Whether this system of incentives will prolong or exacerbate the rule of law crisis remains to be seen. When the results from the carrot approach become visible, the argument for using a larger stick may be even stronger.

5. Conditionality in other programmes and treaties

Part 5 examines how conditionality has operated in other contexts involving the EU as well as under the IMF’s Structural Adjustment Programmes. This provides additional context for conditionality under the RRF and aims to take lessons from how conditionality has operated under these programmes.

(a) Conditionality and the IMF

This section briefly examines key principles observed in the operation of conditionality under the IMF’s Structural Adjustment Programmes (SAPs) (part (i)) as well as EU bailout programmes (ii).

i. Conditionality under Structural Adjustment Programmes

IMF conditionality is different to the types of conditionality seen in EU programmes for several reasons. One of the most important reasons is the differing context in which the IMF operates. It intervenes in countries experiencing balance-of-payments difficulties as well as other financial crises. The IMF’s focus is on macroeconomic performance and remedying the balance-of-payment issues of borrowers while ensuring they do not resort to measures destructive of international prosperity.³⁵ Another key motivation behind this conditionality is that the borrowing country will be able to repay the Fund. Nonetheless, the IMF has considerable experience administering controversial SAPs and its experience contains valuable lessons for the design of other financial programmes, even those as seemingly different as the RRF. There are certain basic commonalities between the conditionality attached to IMF and EU programmes such as the giving out of funding in

³⁴ Alberto Alemanno, ‘Censuring von der Leyen’s Capitulation on the Rule of Law,’ *VerfassungsBlog*, 8 June 2022. Available at: <https://verfassungsblog.de/censuring-von-der-leyens-capitulation-on-the-rule-of-law/>

³⁵ IMF Articles of Agreement, Article I(V).

tranches (as seen under the RRF) and verification procedures that performance criteria have been reached. However, this section focuses on the broader lessons that can be taken from the experience of administering IMF SAPs.

A 2022 IMF Policy Paper outlines the principles that underly conditionality in its longer-term loans under a proposed Resilience and Sustainability Trust. These loans aim to provide “affordable long-term financing to support countries undertaking macro-critical reforms to reduce risks to prospective balance of payment stability”.³⁶ Principles include parsimony, clarity in the specification of conditions, effective coordination with other multilateral institutions, linkage between conditionality and overall programme objectives, and no cross-conditionality.³⁷ The absence of cross-conditionality means that failure to comply with the requirements of one institution ought not to preclude access to financial assistance by another institution. For example, the IMF should not disburse funds based on the assessment of another organisation that the borrower has fulfilled certain conditions. These are longstanding principles that have guided IMF conditionality for decades.

A 2002 IMF Report on Real-Time Assessments of Structural Conditionality elaborates on some of these “lessons”, drawn from administering multiple SAPs. The key lessons outlined in this report include i) parsimony; ii) linkage between conditionality and overall programme objectives; and iii) that a critical mass of reforms may be required to restore market confidence. On the first of these, there is a presumption at the IMF that the coverage of conditionality is parsimonious rather than comprehensive.³⁸ However the presumption is modified in crisis situations as well as when dealing with countries with poor records of past performance. In such cases, extensive and tighter conditionality is found to be warranted.³⁹

Secondly, the 2002 Report found that structural conditionality “must have a clearly identifiable link to the program’s macroeconomic objectives, grounded in an analysis of the country’s balance of payments problems”. Thus, measures covered by conditionality had to be clearly linked to the programme’s overall objectives. Finally, in countries undergoing a crisis, such as massive outflows of private capital, the IMF recommends “a critical mass of front-loaded reforms may be required to restore market confidence”.⁴⁰

³⁶ IMF, Policy Paper Proposal To Establish A Resilience And Sustainability Trust, April 2022, 7.

³⁷ See IMF, Policy Paper Proposal To Establish A Resilience And Sustainability Trust, April 2022, paras 51-52.

³⁸ IMF, Lessons from the Real-Time Assessments of Structural Conditionality, Prepared by the Policy Development and Review Department. Approved by Timothy Geithner (2002) 12.

³⁹ *Ibid*, 3.

⁴⁰ *Ibid*, 11.

ii. Austerity in Europe and EU bailout programmes_

From 2008, the EU implemented bailout programmes to provide financial assistance to Member States facing economic crises. The management of these programmes was overseen by the IMF, the European Commission and the ECB, in a grouping known as the ‘troika’. These programmes were designed to stabilise the affected countries' economies and prevent the spread of financial instability to the rest of the EU. As a condition of receiving assistance, the recipient countries were required to implement certain economic and fiscal reforms, constituting a form of conditionality for this lending. These reforms were intended to address the underlying causes of economic crisis and ensure that the countries were able to repay the loans provided through the bailout programmes.

Conditionality was a key feature of the EU's bailout programmes during this period and it played a critical role in helping to stabilise the economies of several Member States. The IMF's Independent Evaluation Office published a 2016 Report reflecting on the operation of these programmes. One of the issues for IMF staff when designing a programme for an EMU country was preparedness. An earlier assessment placed the likelihood of having to implement a programme in an EMU country as being “extremely unlikely”.⁴¹ The Report emphasises the importance of anticipating such challenges at an early stage to best understand the “specific constraints” they would have to accept when dealing with a euro area member.⁴²

There was also the additional challenge of implementing conditionality in a context where there is a multiplicity of lenders. Related to this was the fact that certain EU policies are under the control of regional institutions, in particular in the area of monetary policy. This caused the IMF to lose its “characteristic agility” with the result that its “technical judgments [were subject] to political pressure”.⁴³ This loss of control led the Evaluation Office to conclude that lessons learnt under previous programmes (including the Asian crisis) were not applied. The principle of prioritisation was not observed. Rather “a long list of structural conditions without prioritization” was imposed.⁴⁴

When designing programmes that involve conditionality, the EU should be mindful of the above principles and their potential relevance. Some of the most pertinent of these lessons

⁴¹ IMF ‘EMU and the Fund—Use of Fund Resources and Use of Euros in the Fund's Operational Budget-Preliminary Considerations’ August (Washington) 1998.

⁴² Independent Evaluation Office of the IMF, Evaluation Report, ‘The IMF and the Crises in Greece, Ireland, and Portugal’ (2016) 38.

⁴³ Ibid.

⁴⁴ Ibid, 25-26.

include:

- 1) when dealing with countries with a poor record of implementing measures, extensive and tighter conditionality is required;
- 2) making the links between milestones and the objectives of the relevant programme as clear as possible;
- 3) The questionable nature of cross-conditionality for example under the RRF and under the Conditionality Regulation;
- 4) When there is a crisis at hand, a critical mass of front-loaded reforms may be required to restore confidence. In relation to Poland and Hungary, this calls into question an approach that would break down the many problems into smaller pieces attaching funding to each minor reform.

(b) Conditionality in other contexts involving the EU

i. Accession

A similar process involving milestones and conditional rewards is the accession process to the EU. Poland and Hungary reached the end of this process with the signing of the Treaty of Accession in 2003, becoming EU Member States in 2004. Pre-accession conditionality in relation to the rule of law evidently was not adhered to post-accession. Reflecting on EU enlargement is not a redundant process as accession talks are currently underway with Albania, Montenegro, North Macedonia, Serbia, and Turkey, while Ukraine and Moldova are also official candidates for membership.

While there are now means (via the Conditionality Regulation and RRF for example) of sanctioning Member States that fail to adhere to EU fundamental values post-accession, neither of these instruments relate to conditionality in the pre-accession phase. What is the best way to ensure that progress made in the pre-accession phase is not discarded once EU membership is attained? Accession treaties need to explicitly address the principle of non-regression in the field of EU values. This provides a potential avenue for solving the ‘Copenhagen dilemma’ – the inability of the Union to enforce its founding values post-accession. The EU needs the tools to ensure that a repeat of the rule of law crisis will not arise in future decades with newly acceded member states. The Accession Treaty is the time to address this, when the EU has maximum leverage rather than scrambling for votes once accession has already taken place.

ii. Brexit negotiations

It is worth stating at the outset that this example is primarily considered for its potential lessons in relation to dealing with a Member State (as the UK was at the time) in times of a crisis with potentially existential ramifications for the EU, as is the case with the rule of law crisis. While the Brexit negotiations did not involve conditionality per se, a form of conditionality was at play when the EU was brokering a free trade agreement with the UK in 2020 (at least in accordance with the definition of conditionality provided in this article)⁴⁵. In this context, the benefit granted was the EU-UK Trade & Cooperation Agreement (TCA). The agreed-upon steps linked to this benefit included concessions granted in the endgame phase of negotiations on issues including the level playing field, governance and fisheries. Though a less pure form of conditionality (particularly as some concessions were made on both sides), certain lessons are still pertinent given the stakes of these negotiations with a (recently departed) EU Member State.

Finalising the EU-UK Trade & Cooperation Agreement (TCA) involved protracted negotiations and brinkmanship leading to the conclusion of a deal on Christmas Eve – one week before the end of the transition period. What guarantees did the EU receive, or to put it another way, what milestones did the UK reach that enabled the EU to sign the TCA?

The EU received sufficient guarantees/ compromises in the key outstanding areas including the level playing field, governance⁴⁶ and fisheries.⁴⁷ The maintenance of a level playing field was perhaps the thorniest final issue between the parties. It was a real fear for the EU that one of the reasons for Brexit was to slash regulation in areas such as labour, social and environmental rights with a view to outcompeting the EU. The TCA ensures that if such divergences occur and there is a material impact on the EU, it can take rebalancing measures to address this situation (Article 9.4 TCA). This provision was one part of a unique solution to a risk that was previously unseen in the negotiations of a free trade agreement.

In terms of lessons for the rule of law crisis, the EU showed its willingness to hold out for an acceptable deal even where it involved waiting until Christmas Eve, the week before the cliff edge of a ‘no-deal’ Brexit would have materialised. This same resolve may be

⁴⁵ Conditionality was defined as arising where one party grants a benefit to another party and this is linked to the latter party taking some step that has been agreed upon by the parties.

⁴⁶ New governance mechanisms were also established to oversee EU-UK relations including a Partnership Council, a dispute settlement system, and many committees.

⁴⁷ On fisheries, access to UK waters was the key issue and a 25% reduction in access was agreed. This was seen as a compromise as the EU wanted to maintain its previous arrangements while the UK wanted a 60% reduction. Politico, EU and UK agree on fisheries access after late scramble, 24 December 2020. Available at: <https://www.politico.eu/article/eu-and-uk-agree-on-brexit-transition-period-for-fisheries-access/>

required in its negotiations on the rule of law crisis. An important differential in terms of the rule of law crisis is that the EU does not have the same degree of leverage as it had in the Brexit negotiations, where ‘no-deal’ would have had even graver consequences for its negotiating partner.

6. The conditionality requirements under the RRF – learning from past experience

This article has outlined a broad range of lessons in the area of conditionality. Conditionality in the context of the RRF is different from the other examples considered for a multitude of reasons and some of the lessons have more relevance to the RRF than others. Key differentiating factors in the context of the RRF include the degree of leverage Poland and Hungary possess and their ability to postpone compliance with milestones. Unlike in many of the examples given, waiting for the winds to change is a plausible tactic for these countries. Poland and Hungary are in a better position to wait for a shift in circumstance than the UK was when the transition period was ending or than a country requiring IMF assistance while experiencing acute balance-of-payments difficulties. They have leverage given the range of decisions requiring unanimity at the EU Council and at some point the rest of the Member States may be willing to compromise and release funds linked to the RRF. A prime example of this is the Commission’s decision to endorse Poland’s NRRP in June 2022.

This article has outlined lessons taken from other programmes involving elements of conditionality. From the IMF, lessons included: recognising the conditions for when tighter conditionality is required; the importance of clarity between milestones and programme objectives; the questionable nature of cross-conditionality; and the question of when it is necessary to front-load a critical mass of reforms.

For other EU programmes lessons included the importance of including binding commitments before giving up leverage (accession). A second lesson was the importance of leverage, sticking to red lines, and being willing to accept a ‘no-deal’ rather than compromising on core values (Brexit negotiations). The Commission should reflect on these lessons and the relevance they may have for implementing the RRF.

2022 has demonstrated that in its negotiations with Poland and Hungary the Commission was willing to endorse their respective NRRPs without fundamental change occurring to the justice systems of either country. Had the Commission not endorsed Hungary’s NRRP in December, the withheld €5.8 billion would have been lost forever.

The Commission has stated that no payment to Hungary will be possible without the full and effective implementation of 27 ‘super milestones’. However in December 2022, Poland reached an agreement with the Commission on legislation that if enacted would lead to the release of the first tranche of Poland’s €35.4 billion in financing.⁴⁸ The early signs from this legislation are that ‘full and effective implementation’ may be easier to satisfy than many would have been hoping for.

If the Commission endorses the plans of member states that have missed the initial deadline for submitting their plan and failed to comply with the first set of milestones, it loses most of the leverage it had in this area (although some member states will seek to comply anyway to ensure swift payment of the funds). If it is likely that the Commission will back down once a deadline approaches and funding may be lost, a different approach should be taken where there is a credible prospect that it will not back down. This could involve staggering the cliff edge for deadlines, i.e. that 20% of the funding would be lost by a certain date rather than 100%.

Difficulties with implementing lessons from past experiences of conditionality in the other contexts considered above include 1) their relevance to the situation at hand, and 2) where they appear to be in conflict with each other or with current practices. One lesson taken from IMF practices concerned the front-loading of a critical mass of reforms in crisis situations. This practice is aimed at restoring market confidence in the midst of a financial crisis and the lesson appears to be that, at a certain point in a crisis, gradual or piecemeal reforms are insufficient to turn the tide. If this lesson were to be applied to the rule of law crisis, it would conflict with any attempt to deal with the rule of law crisis in Poland and Hungary in a piecemeal manner. There is some indication of an acceptance of this approach in relation to Hungary’s 27 rule of law related ‘super milestones’. Prioritisation is also an important principle in IMF programmes and the question may arise as to how this should be balanced against other potential solutions; should certain (rule of law related) milestones be prioritised and addressed first or is front-loading a critical mass of reforms in this area the appropriate solution? To what extent should milestones in relation to the rule of law be prioritised over and interact with conditionality under the other milestones? These other milestones make up 90% of the milestones outlined in Hungary’s NRRP.

⁴⁸ Bloomberg, Poland Agrees With EU on Legal Changes to Free Funds, 13 December 2022. Available at: <https://www.bloomberg.com/news/articles/2022-12-13/poland-says-agreed-with-eu-on-legal-changes-to-free-funds?sref=vtgjJEDZ%2520via&leadSource=verify%20wall>

7. Conclusion

This article considered the nature of conditionality in this new context of EU financial assistance and as it applies under the RRF. If this form of conditionality represents a new system of economic governance,⁴⁹ this article argues that the Commission needs to think carefully about the incentive structures it will create. If milestones become a regular and predictable feature of EU economic governance and reaching them results in the release of significant amounts of financing, this may create a system that incentivises member states to drag their heels on certain reforms knowing that at some point they can be used in a quid pro quo with Brussels in the areas where milestones have been set. Systems of governance must reward the vigilant and reforms or the maintenance of high standards in the areas where ‘milestones’ have been set must not be disincentivised because of a perception that they may become bargaining tools to receive EU funding. This article draws insights from the implementation of conditionality in a variety of circumstances. While conditionality under the Facility is unlike other types of conditionality explored here, there are key principles that are of relevance. These include steadfastness and it being perceived that the Commission will not blink where there is a deadline and the prospect of losing RRF funds looms. One way to do this and not lose the leverage of RRF funds would be to stagger the deadlines and so rather than losing all of the funding, a member state would lose a portion of it if its plan were not approved by a given date. Other key principles include mechanisms that would penalise regression in relation to any milestone.

One would imagine that conditionality in the context of an investment package would be less controversial than other forms of conditionality examined in this article. Of course, this has not proved to be the case as conditionality in the RRF is being used as a tool to address the rule of law crisis in the EU.

Withheld recovery funds represent serious leverage in the rule of law crisis. The Commission must avoid any perception that the rule of law is negotiable and that cross-issue linkages can be made in a kind of bargaining process. The milestones contained in NRRPs represent a form of pragmatism that could only be considered to be a positive step if they bring about the stated goals of the milestones in an unequivocal and enduring manner. The green light for funding must only be given if the proposed reforms are

⁴⁹ Federico Fabbrini, *EU Fiscal Capacity Legal Integration After Covid-19 and the War in Ukraine*, OUP (2022) 72.

brought about in this manner. Respect for fundamental values must be a core component of the RRF but its legacy in this regard remains uncertain for now.

Annex 1

Hungary's 27 'super milestones' as listed in the Annex to the proposal for a Council Implementing Decision on the approval of the recovery and resilience plan for Hungary.

Milestone 160:

Establishment of an Integrity Authority to reinforce the prevention, detection and correction of fraud, conflicts of interest and corruption as well as other illegalities and irregularities concerning the implementation of Union support.

Milestone 166:

Establishment of an Anti-Corruption Task Force to monitor and review the measures taken in Hungary to prevent, detect, prosecute and sanction corruption.

Milestone 169:

Introduction of a specific procedure in the case of special crimes related to the exercise of public authority or the management of public property ('judicial review').

Milestone 171:

Strengthening rules related to asset declarations.

Milestone 174:

Ensuring the transparency of the use of public resources by public interest asset management foundations.

Milestone 175:

Enhancing the transparency of public spending.

Milestone 195:

Setting up of a monitoring and reporting tool ("single-bid reporting tool") to monitor and report on public procurements closed with single-bids financed from Union support or from national resources in accordance with the Single Market Scoreboard methodology.

Milestone 197:

Development of the Electronic Public Procurement System (EPS) to increase transparency.

Milestone 198:

Development of the Electronic Public Procurement System (EPS) to increase transparency.

Milestone 200:

Performance measurement framework for public procurements.

Milestone 201:

Performance measurement framework for public procurements.

Milestone 213:

Strengthening the role and powers of the National Judicial Council to counterbalance the powers of the President of the National Office for the Judiciary.

Milestone 214:

Strengthening judicial independence of the Supreme Court (Kúria).

Milestone 215:

Removing obstacles to references for preliminary rulings to the Court of Justice of the European Union.

Milestone 216:

Reform regarding the review of final judgments by the Constitutional Court.

Milestone 217:

Reinforced legal provisions setting out implementation, monitoring, and audit and control arrangements to guarantee the sound use of Union support.

Milestone 218:

Reinforced legal provisions setting out implementation, monitoring, and audit and control arrangements to guarantee the sound use of Union support.

Milestone 219:

Reinforced legal provisions setting out implementation, monitoring, and audit and control arrangements to guarantee the sound use of Union support.

Milestone 220:

An effective anti-fraud and anti-corruption strategy for the implementation, audit and control of Union support.

Milestone 221:

An effective anti-fraud and anti-corruption strategy for the implementation, audit and control of Union support.

Milestone 222:

Full and effective use of the Arachne system for all Union support.

Milestone 223:

Full and effective use of the Arachne system for all Union support.

Milestone 224:

Establishment of a Directorate of Internal Audit and Integrity to reinforce the control of conflicts of interest when implementing Union support.

Milestone 225:

Ensuring the capacity for the EUTAF to effectively carry out its tasks.

Milestone 226:

Strengthening cooperation with OLAF to reinforce the detection of fraud related to the implementation of Union support.

Milestone 227:

Effective implementation, control and audit of the Recovery and Resilience Plan and the protection of the financial interests of the Union.

Milestone 228:

Effective implementation, control and audit of the Recovery and Resilience Plan and the protection of the financial interests of the Union.